

STUDY ON THE IMPACT LEVEL OF ADOLESCENT'S ACADEMIC STRESS, BEHAVIOR & EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS ON THE QUALITY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS

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Abstract

The quality of Interpersonal relationships(IR) of adolescents has been marked as one of the core factors associated with successful educational transitions, however, little is known about the reciprocal link between academic stress(AS) and behavioral emotional problems (BEP), with even less known about how these two constructs impact adolescents quality of IR. Study investigated the IR, AS, and BEP of adolescents. The data were collected from 120secondary school students(M=50%,F=50%) (12-16age;7th-10th grade), 120Parents,(F=66.67%, M=33.33) and 100 teachers (M=50%,F=50%) from 10 schools through a simple random sampling method. The Parents and Peer Attachment Inventory-Revised (Gullone & Robinson, 2005) was used to examining the IR with fathers, mothers and peers, and Adolescents' Behavioral and Emotional Problem Scale (Dwivedi 2019) was used to assess BEP (teachers & parents' perspectives). For examining AS, Scale for assessing academic stress (Sinha, Sharma and Mahendra 2001) was used. Descriptive and inferential statistics were performed in SPSS version 23. The findings of the study suggest that there is a moderately positive correlation between adolescents AS and BEP (.494,p<0.01). Furthermore AS (F(2,117)=41.624,p<0.001, and BEP(F(2,117)=41.624,p<0.001, successfully predicted the communication, alienation, and trust components of IR of adolescent at (b = -1.158,p<.001), (b = -.395,p<.001) level. No significant group difference was found in adolescents quality of IR between(male/female) (t(118)= -.157,p=.876), (urban/rural)(t(118) =2.265,p = .025), single-multiple child (t(118) =1.993, p=.049) and family type (F2, 117=.508,p>.005) of the participants.

Keywords: Adolescents, Interpersonal relationships, Behavior and emotional problems, Academic stress, Academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence as a transition phase between childhood to adulthood is the most stressful time for a human being. Adolescent goes through a lot of changes at this time, in terms of both physical and mental. It is the time when they start to explore the world around them, make close peer groups, try new things, make idols, and involve themselves in romantic relationships. (Noronha, Laveena & Govindaraju, 2016)

Relationships of adolescents with parents also go through a lot of changes. These changes can both be positive and negative. Both mother and father need to put an equal amount of time and effort to build a good positive relationship with their children so that they feel comfortable discussing issues from a very early age. (Georgiou & Symeou, 2018)

A positive relationship with the parents of an adolescent can give them the confidence, support, and motivation to thrive to be a better person and to do good in their academics as well as in career goals. (Sekaran, Ashok, Kamath, 2020)

It will give them the required environment where they can learn new skills, explore new skills and advance their knowledge. If parents provide a positive environment around them during this period it will give them the space to explore their goals and expand their knowledge more safely. (Caridade, Sousa & Pimenta Dinis 2020). A negative relationship with parents can lead to a disaster in this period. Most of the time at this period adolescents don't prefer to spend much time with their parents. Negative relations with parents can lead to a sense of loneliness, low confidence where they may feel unworthy and unaccepted. (Russell, 2013; Seo & Kwon (2016). This negative space can influence adolescents in a way where they may learn about their surroundings from bad sources, get involved in unsafe things, consume substances, and face many behavior and emotional issues. (McCormick, Meghan, Cappella, Elise, O'Connor, Erin, McClowry & Sandee. 2013).

Peer relationship dynamics also change a lot at this time. Peers become closer than ever, sense of belonging increases in adolescence. Peers become more important figures in this period when adolescent wants to spend most of their time with their peer groups, share things, and discuss interests and issues. Feeling of jealousy, and competitiveness also increases between adolescent's peer groups. A negative relationship with peers of an adolescent can create a lot of problems and hugely impact their lives whereas a positive relationship with peers can be an important support system for adolescents period. (Montague, Cavendish, Enders & Dietz, 2010)

The interpersonal relationships of adolescents are a crucial factor in determining how they will face and deal with these changes and stressful situations. (Miranda Sentse & Robert D. Laird 2010; Yap ching ching 2015)

Apart from changes and issues in interpersonal relationship, academics is a major reason why adolescent faces a lot of stress. Between the age of 12-18, adolescents were mostly in class 7th to class 12th. This is the time when studies get more complex and competition to get good marks, securing good colleges and jobs gets higher. (Wang, Xia, Li, Wilson, Bush & Peterson 2016) Adolescents spend most of their time in their studies, preparing for exams or classwork. Parents also started to increase their efforts and time in their children so that they can perform well in their academics, and with that their expectations also started to increase. (Ashok, 2019).

With the pressure from academics, competition between peers also increases. This is the time when because of high stress, adolescents started having issues in an interpersonal relationships with their parents, peers as well as teachers. (Noronha, Laveena & M., Govindaraju 2016; Siwach, N. & Devi 2014). Academic stress can be from multiple reasons, being not able to perform according to their capabilities, meet their parent's expectations, pressure from school, teacher's parents and finally getting behind in competition with their classmates. (Deb, Sibnath, Strodl, Esben & Sun, 2015; Nandamuri, Purna Prabhakar & Gowthami 2011). Apart from creating problems in interpersonal relationships, academic stress may also be a major reason for different types of behavior and emotional problems seen in this age ranging from carelessness, aggressive behavior, bullying behavior, impulsivity, substance use, stubbornness, sadness, fear, withdrawal, and shyness. (Bataineh 2013; Nakano, Yamazaki, Teshirogi, Kubo, Ogawa, Kameo & Koyama, 2022). This behavior and emotional problems create a lot of issues in adolescent interpersonal relations. It also affects the goals of the child, affects their studies, health, their mental health, and well-being, and put immense stress on both the adolescent and parents. (Liu & Lu 2012).

In the present study, the researcher studied the relationship between variables like behavior and emotional problems, academic stress, and Interpersonal relationship. The researcher studied how these three variables are interrelated with each other and how each variable affects the another. In the present research, the researcher studied the nature of the relationship between academic stress and behavior and emotional problems, also how academic stress of an adolescent can impact their behavior and emotional problems. The further researcher also studied how the behavior and emotional problems of an adolescent perceived by parents and teachers can impact their interpersonal relationships with mothers, fathers, and peers. The present research also studied the mediating effect of interpersonal relationships on academic stress and behavior and emotional problems. Lastly, the researcher also studied the group difference between male-female, single-multiple children, and an urban-rural adolescent sample of the present study in terms of academic stress and behavior and emotional problems.

Studies around the world have been investigating academic stress, interpersonal relationship, behavior, and emotional problems, however, researchers simultaneously studying these three variables on adolescent participants and how academic stress may be a major reason for their behavior and emotional problems and eventually affecting the quality of the interpersonal relationship of an adolescent with parents and peers remain a gap in the currently available literature. Apart from that present study also looking at commonness and possible differences in mentioned variables in a rural and urban adolescent population.

Method

A descriptive research design was used for conducting the present study. The present study was conducted at 10 schools both (government and private) in 4 districts of Assam (Sivasagar, Charaideo, Kamrup, and Jorhat).

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the nature of the relationship between adolescents' academic stress and behavioral & emotional problems.
2. To study the impact level of adolescents' academic stress on Interpersonal relationships with peers parents and teachers.
3. To study the impact level of adolescents' behavioral & emotional problems on Interpersonal relationships with peers parents and teachers.
4. To compare the Interpersonal relationship of adolescents based on gender (male/female), location (urban/rural), single-multiple child, and family type of the participants.

Hypothesis

Alternate hypotheses were created based on the stated objectives of the present research work.

- 1) H1- There will be an association between adolescents' academic stress and behavioral & emotional problems.
- 2) H2- Academic stress will impact adolescents' Interpersonal relationships with their mother, father, and peers.
- 3) H3- Behavior & emotional problems will impact adolescents' Interpersonal relationships with mothers, fathers, and peers.
- 4) H4- There will be a difference between adolescents' Interpersonal relationships based on gender (male/female), location (urban/rural), single-multiple child, and family type of the participants.

Population

The participants of the present study include all the School students from class 7th standard to 10th standard (12-16 age group), their Parents, and school teachers in the district of Sivasagar, Charaideo, Kamrup, and Jorhat of Assam under the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) and Board of Secondary Education Assam (SEBA).

Sample and sampling method:

A total of 120 school-going adolescents, Their Parents, and 100 school Teachers were selected from 10 schools in 4 different districts namely (Sivasagar, Charaideo, Kamrup, and Jorhat) Assam. The selected sample size in the study was between 12-16 years old studying in 7th to 10th standard and school teachers working in these secondary schools.

Simple random sampling has been adopted to collect the required data for the study. The researcher randomly selects 10 schools from the 4 mentioned districts with the help of chits. The sample is collected from 7th to 10th standard school students (12-16 age) studying in the selected schools of districts Charaideo, Sivasagar, Kamrup, and Jorhat. Participants from government & private schools, and urban & rural schools both were included in this study.

Instruments

The Inventory of Parents and Peer Attachment-Revised (Gullone & Robinson, 2005) was used to examine the interpersonal relationship of adolescents with fathers, mothers, and peers, and the Adolescents' Behavioral and Emotional Problem Scale (Supriya Dwivedi 2019) was used to assess adolescent behavioral and emotional problems from the teachers and parents' perspectives. Furthermore, the Academic Stress of adolescents was measured through Scale for assessing academic stress (Sinha, Sharma, and Mahendra 2001) was used. Age, Gender, and family details have been taken from demographic details sheets.

Data collection procedure and timeline

The researcher collected the required data by administrating the stated instruments on the school-going adolescents studying in 7th to 10th standard in various government and private schools of 4 different districts. For adolescents, personal

details demographic details sheet and school records has been used with the consent of the school authorities and students.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics-

Table 1: Participants Gender frequency distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male adolescent	60	50.0
Female adolescent	60	50.0
Father participant	40	33.33
Mother participant	80	66.67
Male teacher	50	50.0
Female teacher	50	50.0

Present study sample, out of 120 adolescents participants 50 percent are male and 50 percent of the participants were female. Whereas from 120 parents participants 66.67 percent are mothers and only 33.33 percent participants are father. Lastly 50 percent of teachers are male and 50 percent are female out of 100 participants.

Table 2: Participants Age frequency distribution

Age	Frequency	Percentage
13	15	12.5
14	28	23.3
15	55	45.8
16	22	18.3
Total	120	100.0

In the present study out of 120 participants 12.5 are of 13 years old, 23.3 percent are 14 years old, followed by 45.8 are 15 years old and 18.3 percent adolescents are 16 years old.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of Rural/ Urban population.

Urban/ Rural	Frequency	Percent
Rural	86	71.7
Semi- Urban/ Urban	34	28.3
Total	120	100.0

In the above table frequency distribution of rural/ urban population has been given. 71.7 percent of adolescent and parents participants are from Rural areas of Sivasagar and Charaideo and 28.3 percent of adolescent and their parents are from Urban and semi urban areas from the cities like Guwahati and Jorhat.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of number of single- multiple children adolescent participants.

Siblings	Frequency	Percent
No siblings	40	33.3
siblings	80	66.7
Total	120	100.0

Above table shows the frequency distribution of single/ multiple children sample in the present study. Out of 120 adolescent participants 66.7 percent are having siblings and 33.3 percent don't have siblings.

Table 5: Frequency distribution of adolescent participants family type

Family type	Frequency	Percent
Joint family	61	50.8
Nuclear family	49	40.8
Single parent	10	8.3
Total	120	100.0

In the above table frequency distribution of family type of adolescents were given. Out of 120 adolescents and parents participants 50.8 percent are from joint family, followed by 40.8 percent are from nuclear family and lastly 8.3 are from single family home.

Table 6: Frequency distribution of adolescent quality of interpersonal relationship with mother, father and peers.

Quality of Interpersonal relationship	Frequency	Percent
Low level	10	8.3
Moderate level	94	78.3
Good level	16	13.3
Total	120	100.0

In the above table frequency distribution of adolescents quality of interpersonal relationship were presented taken with the help of The Inventory of Parents and Peer Attachment-Revised (Gullone & Robinson, 2005) scale. Out of 120 adolescents of Present study 78.3 percent of adolescents are having moderate level of relationship with their mother father and peers followed by 13.3 percent participants are having good quality relationship and lastly 8.3 percent are having low level of interpersonal relationship with their parents and peers.

Table 7: Frequency distribution of adolescents behavior and emotional problems.

Behavior & emotional problems	Frequency	Percent
Low level	92	76.7
Average level	23	19.2
High level	5	4.2
Very high level	0	0.0
Total	120	100.0

In the above table frequency distribution of adolescents behavior and emotional problems were presented measured with the help of Adolescents' Behavioral and Emotional Problem Scale (Supriya Dwivedi 2019) scale. Data shows that out of 120 participants 76.7 percent adolescents are showing low level of behavior and emotional problems, followed by 19.2 percent showing moderate level and only 4.2 percent participants are showing high level of behavior and emotional problems

Table 8: Frequency distribution of adolescents level of academic stress.

Academic stress level	Frequency	Percent
Low level	6	5.0
Moderate level	47	39.2
High level	67	55.8
Total	120	100.0

In the above table frequency distribution of adolescents level of academic stress is given measured with the help of Scale for assessing academic stress (Sinha, Sharma and Mahendra 2001). data from the present study showed that out of 120 participants 5 percent are having low level of academic stress followed by 39.2 percent are having moderate level of academic stress and 55.8 percent of the participants are showing high level of academic stress.

Inferential statistics

Table 9: Association Between adolescents academic stress and behavior problems & emotional problems.

Variable	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation	Co-efficient of correlation(r)	P
Academic stress	30	15.6667	3.93505	.494	<0.01
Behavior problem & emotional problem	78	32.175	6.40596		

By analyzing both the variable Academic stress and Behavior & emotional problems of Adolescents with the help Pearson correlation, results indicated that there is a positive and moderately significant correlation at the (.494 $p < 0.01$) level. Indicating that there is a positive relationships between academic stress and Behavior & emotional problems hence accepting the H1 that there is a moderately significant association between academic stress with Behavior & emotional problems of Adolescents.

Multiple regression of Academic stress, Behavior & emotional problems on Interpersonal relationships.

The Multiple regression test of Academic stress (AS) and behavior & emotional problems (BEP) of adolescents have a significant impact on Interpersonal relationship (IR).

Results shows that Academic stress (AS) significantly predicted Interpersonal relationship (IR), $F(2, 117) = 41.624, p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Academic stress shall play a major role in shaping Interpersonal relationship (IR) ($b = -1.158, p < .001$). Results direct the negative effect of Academic stress. lastly, the R square = .416 indicates that the model explains 41.6% variance in Interpersonal relationship, Accepting the H2, that Academic stress will significantly impact the Interpersonal relationship of adolescents.

Furthermore, Results shows Behavior & emotional problem (BEP) significantly predicted Interpersonal relationship, $F(2, 117) = 41.624, p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Behavior & emotional problem (BEP) shall play a important role in shaping Interpersonal relationship ($b = -.395, p < .001$). Study results depict the negative effect of Behavior & emotional problems (BEP). lastly, the R square = .416 indicates that the model explains 41.6% variance in Interpersonal relationship, Accepting the H3,

that Behavior & emotional problems (BEP) will significantly impact the Interpersonal relationship of adolescents.

Table 10: Impact of academic stress, Behavior & emotional problems on Adolescents Interpersonal Relationship.

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R Square	F	t-Value	P-Value	Hypothesis Supported
H2	AS → IR	1.158	416	41.624	5.846	000	YES
H3	BEP → IR	395	416	41.624	3.205	000	YES

Note: *p< 0.05. IR: Interpersonal Relationship, BEP: Behavioral and Emotional Problem, AA- Academic Achievement.

Independent Sample t-test between Male-Female, urban-rural participants and single-multiple child participants Respondents.

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the Adolescent's Interpersonal relationship of Male-Female, Urban-Rural, single- multiple child For Interpersonal relationship.

For male-female there were no significant differences (t (118) = -.157, p = .876) in scores for Males (M = 88.8854, SD =9.45876) and Females (M=88.6131, SD = 9.50721). The magnitude of the differences in the means (mean difference = -.27232, 95% CI: -3.70792 to 3.16328) was very small. Hence, H4 was not supported.

Similarly, for urban-rural participants there were no significant differences (t (118) = 2.265, p = .025) in scores for Urban participants (M = 85.7059, SD = 8.85217) and Rural participants (M= 89.9651, SD = 10.30928). The magnitude of the differences in the means (mean difference = 4.25923, 95% CI: -.53529 to7.98317) was very small. Hence, H4 was not supported.

lastly, for single- multiple child participants there were no significant differences (t (118) =1.993, p = .049) in scores for Single child participants (M = 91.1583, SD =7.80057) and Multiple child participants (M= 87.5583, SD = 9.99446). The magnitude of the differences in the means (mean difference = 3.60000, 95% CI: -.02343 to 7.17657) was very small. Hence, H4 was not supported.

Table 11: Differences in adolescent's Interpersonal relationship between Male and Female, Urban-Rural participants and single-multiple child participants.

				Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
				F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
		Mean	SD									Lower	Upper
DV	Male	88.8854	9.45876	.010	.922	-.157	118	.876	-.27232	1.73491	-3.70792	3.16328	
	Female	88.6131	9.50721										
DV	Urban	85.7059	8.85217	.220	.640	2.265	118	.025	4.25923	1.88052	.53529	7.98317	
	Rural	89.9651	10.30928										
DV	Single child	91.1583	7.80057	3.466	.065	1.993	118	.049	3.60000	1.80610	.02343	7.17657	
	Multiple child	87.5583	9.99446						3.60000	1.66428			

M Mean; SD Standard Deviation

One Way ANOVA

H4 there are significant differences in Interpersonal relationship of adolescent with father, mother and peers in different family structures.

The hypothesis tests different family structures. Participants were divided into 3 groups (Group 1: Joint family; Group 2: Nuclear family; Group 3: Single-parent family). The ANOVA results suggest that the Adolescent Interpersonal relationship does not differ significantly ($F_{2, 117} = .508, p > .005$).

Table 12: Differences in adolescent's Interpersonal relationship between family types.

				Test of Homogeneity of Variances		ANOVA	
				Levene's Statistic	Sig.		
CIP	Joint	88.15	9.620	.192	.825	.508	.603
	Nuclear	89.78	9.407				
	Single-parent	87.43	8.930				

M Mean; *SD* Standard Deviation

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the researcher investigated the relationship and effect of academic stress and behavior & emotional problems on the interpersonal relationship of adolescents with parents and peers. The researcher studied the nature of the relationship between adolescents' academic stress and behavior & emotional problems. Furthermore study also examined how academic stress and behavior & emotional problems affect the interpersonal relationship of adolescents with father, mother, and peers. Lastly, the present study also examined the possible group difference in the interpersonal relationship of adolescents between male-female, urban-rural, single-multiple children, and types of families.

Data shows that out of 120 adolescent participants 78.3 percent of participant shares a moderate level of interpersonal relationship with their mother father and peers, followed by 13.3 of participants having a good level and 8.3 percent of participants having a low level of interpersonal relationship with their parents and peers.

While exploring the behavior & emotional problems of the present study participants from their teacher's and parent's perspective results indicated that 76.7 percent of adolescents having a low level of behavior and emotional problems. 19.2 percent of participants are having a moderate level of behavior and emotional problems, whereas 4.2 percent of adolescents show high-level behavior and emotional problems.

Study results showed that out of 120 adolescent participants 5 percent are having low levels of academic stress. 39.2 percent of adolescent participants in the present study are having a moderate level of academic stress whereas 55.8 percent of the sample are having a high level of academic stress.

The present study investigated the relationship between adolescents' academic stress and behavior & emotional problems by using the Pearson correlation method. Results showed that there is a moderately positive and statistically significant correlation at ($b = .494, p < .001$) level between adolescents' academic stress and behavior & emotional problems. Indicating that there is a positive relationship between

adolescents' academic stress and behavior and emotional problems. (Siwach, N., & Devi, N. 2014; McCormick., et al. 2013; Bataineh 2013; Nakano., et al, 2022).

While examining the impact level of academic stress on adolescents' interpersonal relationships with their parents and peers, it was found in the present study that academic stress significantly predicted adolescents' interpersonal relationships with their parents and peers. Indicating that academic stress plays a significant role in shaping adolescents' interpersonal relationships ($b = -1.158$, $p < .001$). Results direct the negative effect of academic stress on the interpersonal relationships of adolescents. (Nandamuri, Purna Prabhakar & Gowthami, Ch., 2011; Noronha, Laveena & M., Govindaraju 2016; Liu, Y., & Lu, Z. 2012).

Furthermore, results also showed behavior and emotional problems of adolescents significantly predicated interpersonal relationships with parents and peers. Indicating that the behavior and emotional problems of adolescents play a significant role in shaping their interpersonal relationships ($b = -.395$, $p < .001$). Results direct the negative effect of behavior and emotional problems on adolescents' interpersonal relationships with their parents and peers. (Laizane, I. 2012).

Moreover, the R square = .416 depicts that the model explains 41.6% of the variance in interpersonal relationships. Meaning academic stress and behavior & emotional problems of adolescents negatively influence interpersonal relationships. Results of the present study concluded that if adolescents' academic stress and behavior problems & emotional problems were found to be on the higher side their quality of interpersonal relationships with their mother, father, and peers in terms of communication, alienation, and trust component will be low. (Miranda, S. & Robert, D. L., 2010)

Lastly, study results indicated that there was no significant difference in adolescents' quality of Interpersonal relationships based on the gender (male/female), location (urban/rural), and single-multiple child of the present study participants.

Also, a similar non-significant group difference was found in adolescents' quality of interpersonal relationships with their parents and peers between joint, nuclear, and single-parent families at .603 level.

Research findings contributed to the present body of literature in variables like the interpersonal relationship of an adolescent with their parents and peers, academic stress, and behavior & emotional problems. The present study was an earnest attempt to understand and brings light to a complex relationship between behavior, emotional problems of adolescent, interpersonal relationship with different people, and stress in academics.

The present study was one of the first attempts to understand this variable in different group contexts like urban-rural populations, adolescents from different family types, and adolescents coming from single- multiple-child families. Findings will help concerned authorities, school administration, teachers, and parents to understand and deal effectively with adolescents' academic stress and different behavioral and emotional issues. It will help teachers and parents strengthen the relationship dynamics of the adolescent with their surroundings as well as help and guide them efficiently in their academics.

CONCLUSION

The overarching goal of psychology as a field is to advance the innovation, communication, and application of psychological knowledge to benefit human lives and societies (American Psychological Association, 2015). The present study has attempted to address this mission with a conceptual framework and initial data for adolescents' academic stress, different behavior & emotional problems, and their impact level on interpersonal relationship dynamics, in different contexts like urban-rural populations, different family structures, and single-multiple child families. Findings will provide required information to education boards, organizations, teachers, and parents to understand and deal more effectively with adolescents' academic stress and behavioral changes. Results will also provide important insight to teachers and parents to improve the interpersonal relationship of the adolescent with peers, teachers, and parents with the help of new curricula and interventions.

Limitations and future direction

The present study tried to investigate the relationship and impact level between variables like academic stress, behavioral and emotional problems, and interpersonal relationships of adolescents. Only a few districts of Assam were included in the present study, it is recommended for future researchers that more states and districts from different parts of India can be taken in extending the current work to a larger population. Both quantitative and qualitative research can be conducted in future research to get a more clear picture and detailed information about the variables of the present study. Furthermore, longitudinal research can be conducted to understand variables like behavior & emotional problems, academic stress, and relationship dynamics among adolescents with time.

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Author Contributions

All of the authors contributed to the study's conception and design. Literature review, data collection, and data analysis were performed by BB. The analyzed data and its description were reviewed by PP and AS. The first draft of the manuscript was written by BB and AS and PP commented on previous versions of the manuscript to help it improve. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Availability of Data and Material The data analyzed for this paper are available from the author upon reasonable request meeting institutional guidelines.

Declarations

All authors have given full assurance that the manuscript submitted is not under review elsewhere.

Conflict of interest The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethics Approval APA ethical guidelines were followed in conducting the study, including taking informed consent, ensuring participants have the right to withdraw at any point, maintaining anonymity, and ensuring data safety.

Consent to Participate Participants signed the consent form before taking part in the research.

Consent for Publication Participants gave their consent for the publication of their data, provided that their identity will not be revealed

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